

Simulation of the CO₂ Hydrate – Water Interfacial Energy: the Mold Integration–Guest methodology (Supporting Material)

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I. NUMBER OF WATER MOLECULES IN THE HYDRATE PHASE

According to the main article, we have determined the time evolution of n_h , the number of water molecules in the CO₂ hydrate slab, for twenty-five different well radius, ranging from 0.507 (0.16 σ) to 1.267 Å (0.40 σ), with $\sigma = 3.1668$ Å the diameter associated with the Lennard-Jones intermolecular potential of the TIP4P/ice model of water. All the results are presented in Figures S1, S2, and S3. As it is explained in the main paper, it is possible to identify three different scenarios:

- (a) **Scenario I**, corresponding to systems with $r_w \leq 0.665$ Å (0.21 σ) in which none of the trajectories exhibits induction period and system always crystallizes if simulation runs are sufficiently long (no free energy barrier between the fluid and solid phases exists). See Figure S1.
- (b) **Scenario II**, corresponding to intermediate values with 0.697 Å $\leq r_w \leq 1.235$ Å (0.22 $\sigma \leq r_w \leq 0.37\sigma$) in which at least one trajectory shows an induction period, i.e., n_h does not grow, on average, from $t=0$ ns. See Figures S1, S2, and S3. The common behavior of these systems, according to scenario II, is that all trajectories exhibit, on average, a monotonous growing of n_h with time, indicating that although systems have free energy barriers between the liquid and solid phases, they are able to overcome them and crystallize if simulations are long enough.
- (c) **Scenario III**, corresponding to systems with $r_w \geq 1.267$ Å ($r_w \geq 0.40\sigma$) in which none of them exhibit, on average, monotonic increasing of n_h with time due to the existence of a free energy barrier between the fluid and solid that does not allow the system to crystallize. See Figure S3.

II. MULTIMEDIA CONTENT

We have included here the list of complementary multimedia results (movies) obtained from previous simulations performed by Algaba and collaborators⁷, and from calculations performed in this work. In particular, these results correspond to Molecular Dynamics (MD) computer simulations in the $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble starting from an initial and equilibrated liquid-liquid configuration

FIG. S1. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (40 MPa and 287 K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 12k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

of the $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ binary mixture considered in the main paper. All simulations have been carried out at 40 MPa and 287 K.

We consider two different sets of simulations. In the first set, the Mold Integration - Host or MI-H methodology is used. A mold of attractive sites, in the center of the simulation box, is placed at the equilibrium positions of the oxygen atoms of water molecules along two principal planes of the sI structure of the CO_2 hydrate. In this case, Algaba and coworkers used $N_w = 56$ attractive interacting sites, with $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$ and two different well values: $r_w = 0.76 \text{ \AA}$, a value below the optimal radius value $r_w^0 = 1.19 \text{ \AA}$ (MIH-crystallization.movie.mpg), and $r_w = 1.457 \text{ \AA}$, a value above the optimal radius value (MIH-no-crystallization.movie.mpg). In the first case, according to the work of Algaba *et al.*, the systems crystallizes completely since there is no free energy barrier

FIG. S2. The conditions and meaning of the curves are the same as in Figure S1.

between the hydrate and the aqueous solution. Contrary, in the second case the system is not able to overcome the free energy barrier but is able to form a thin hydrate slab. See the movies and the original work of Algaba and collaborators².

In the second set, we use the Mold Integration - Guest or MI-G methodology presented in the main paper. In this case, the mold of attractive sites are placed, in the center of the simulation box, at the equilibrium positions of the carbon atoms of CO₂ molecules along two principal planes of the sI structure of the CO₂ hydrate. Note that the mold is occupying the central positions of the T and D cages of the hydrate, as indicated in the main paper. According to this work, we use $N_w = 16$ attractive interacting sites, with $\varepsilon = 12k_B T$ and two different values of the well radius: $r_w = 0.665 \text{ \AA}$, a value below the optimal radius value $r_w^0 = 0.21 \text{ \AA}$ (MIG-crystallization.movie.mpg), and $r_w = 1.267 \text{ \AA}$, a value above the optimal radius value (MIG-no-crystallization.movie.mpg). As it occurs with the MI-H method, in the first case the system crystallizes completely since there is no free energy barrier between the hydrate and the aqueous solution. Contrary, in the second case the system is not able to overcome the free energy barrier but is able to form a thin hydrate

FIG. S3. The conditions and meaning of the curves are the same as in Figure S1.

slab. See the corresponding movies described in the next paragraph.

Red and white licorice representation corresponds to oxygen and hydrogen atoms of water, respectively. In the movies obtained using the MI-H methodology, green spheres (van der Waals representation) correspond to carbon and oxygen atoms of CO_2 . In the movies obtained using the MI-G methodology, yellow and blue spheres (van der Waals representation) correspond to carbon atom and oxygen atoms of CO_2 , respectively. Finally, in the case of simulations using the MI-H methodology, the 56 yellow spheres (van der Waals representation) correspond to the mold attractive sites using $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$ and $r_w = 0.76$ (crystallization) and 1.456 \AA (no crystallization). In the case of simulations using the MI-G methodology, the 16 magenta spheres (van der Waals representation) correspond to the mold attractive sites using $\varepsilon = 12k_B T$ and $r_w = 0.665$ (crystallization) and 1.267 \AA (no crystallization).

Here we provide the list of the files containing the movies indicating the time simulated in each case:

- Simulation using the MI-H methodology with crystallization (200 ns):
video-MIH-crystallization.mp4.
- Simulation using the MI-H methodology without crystallization (200 ns):
video-MIH-no-crystallization.mp4.
- Simulation using the MI-G methodology with crystallization (100 ns):
video-MIG-crystallization.mpg.
- Simulation using the MI-G methodology without crystallization (50 ns):
video-MIG-no-crystallization.mpg.